

Clinical Profile of Post-Menopausal Women with Urinary Tract InfectionZoya Hussain¹, Anuradha Deuri², Monalisha Saikia Borah³¹Post Graduate Trainee, Department of General Medicine, GMCH, Guwahati²Professor, Department of General Medicine, GMCH, Guwahati³Scientist C, Multidisciplinary Research Unit, GMCH, Guwahati

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Zoya Hussain Z

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: An annual issue for millions of people worldwide are urinary tract infections (UTIs), which are a frequent and chronic medical condition. The most prevalent bacterial illness among women overall, and among postmenopausal women specifically, is urinary tract infection (UTI). Regarding age and general state, two groups of elderly women with recurrent UTIs should be distinguished: elderly institutionalized women with or without a catheter and healthy, young postmenopausal women between the ages of 50 and 70 who are neither institutionalized nor catheterized.

Methods: A study population of 134 post-menopausal women, attending OPD or admitted to Department of General Medicine, Gauhati Medical College and Hospital and study duration was from December 2023 to July 2024. The co-morbidities, recurrence of UTI and the type of organisms isolated from urine sample were studied. Data were analysed using PRISM software, version 8.0.

Results: The most common age group of prevalence of UTI in the most menopausal female was in 44-52 years (44%). The overall the recurrence rate was 41.3% and the rate was highest in the >80 years age group (77%). There was statistically significant association between diabetes mellitus and UTI recurrence with p value of 0.03. The most common organism isolated was E. coli 76.8%, in urine cultures. It was also responsible for adverse outcomes.

Conclusion: The study revealed a higher recurrence rate with advanced age among postmenopausal women. There was two times more risk of developing UTI in patients with Diabetes Mellitus. E. coli was the most common organism responsible.

Keywords: Urinary Tract infection (UTI), Recurrence, Diabetes Mellitus (DM), E. coli.

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Introduction

The term "urinary tract infection" (UTI) is a general word that refers to a variety of infectious syndromes that can affect any part of the urinary tract, from the kidneys to the urethra. UTIs constitute a few of the most prevalent infections. Approximately 50% to 60% of women have at least one episode of UTI in their lifespan.

The basic mechanism is the colonization of bacteria of the periurethral space or urethra or moving up and entering the bladder, resulting in an inflammatory reaction. Usually, the microorganisms that cause this are gastrointestinal (GI) tract-derived and are referred to as Enterobacteriaceae together; examples consist of *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Proteus mirabilis*. A second method of bacteria in the bloodstream causing UTIs moving to the bladder or kidneys, however this is quite uncommon [3]. Female sex, recent sexual activity, diabetes mellitus, and structural or functional urological abnormalities are risk factors for urinary

tract infections. In women of all ages, urinary tract infections (UTIs) are the most prevalent type of bacterial infections. Research on UTIs has mostly focused on young women, even though older women have a higher rate of bacteriuria. Women are more likely to acquire UTI due to the close proximity of urethra to both bladder as well the vagina and rectum. The fact that UTI symptoms are rarely evident, even if the bacterial colonies manage to make it to the bladder and start growing there, is another noteworthy aspect of these colonies [4].

Depending on the site of infection and the state of the host's body, UTIs can be categorized as "lower" or "upper", either simple or complicated. Lower UTIs affect the urethra and the bladder, while upper UTIs affect the kidneys and ureters, similar to pyelonephritis. Moreover, functional or anatomical urinary tract infections (UTIs) without anomalies is referred to as simple UTIs. Conversely, any cases other than uncomplicated

UTIs are considered complicated UTIs [5]. Pain in the suprapubic area, pain during urination with or without frequency, or obvious haematuria are the typical symptoms of lower UTIs. Symptoms of an upper urinary tract infection (UTI) can include constitutional ones like fever ($>100^{\circ}\text{F}$), chills, nausea, vomiting, discomfort at the costovertebral angle, and nausea, with or without cystitis symptoms [5]. Fever is typically associated with complicated types of UTIs and is infrequent in lower UTIs [6]. It is important to understand that these symptoms do indicate a urinary tract infection in the individual but are not confirmatory. If a patient has a history of recurrent UTIs, the likelihood of actually having the infection rises to 84%–92%. Moreover, the previously described symptoms are infrequently displayed by older women with UTIs. Urinary incontinence may be the only symptom they have [4].

Patients with diabetes often experience morbidity and mortality due to infections. There is evidence that the most prevalent bacterial infection among diabetic individuals is urinary tract infection (UTI). Urine with a high glucose content can be a significant source of nutrition for bacteria [7,8]. As a result, bacteria can grow and lay the groundwork for an infection. Additionally, a high urine glucose level can encourage the colonization of microorganisms in the urine.

Methods

Study design and setting: Ours is a tertiary care teaching institute in North Eastern part of the country. This was a single-institute prospective observation study of clinical data collected from patients during December 2023 to July 2024. Data collection was started after obtaining permission from the Institutional Ethics Committee. Convenience sampling technique was used. The

study followed the guidelines laid down in the Declaration of Helsinki (2008).

Sample Size: Considering the prevalence of urinary tract infection in postmenopausal group of women to be around 20% in the area a total of 134 patients who fulfilled the inclusion criteria were taken up for the study.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Patients admitted with symptoms associated with UTI.
2. Post- menopausal women.
3. Patients providing informed consent for the study

Exclusion Criteria: Pre-menopausal women and patients not giving informed consent were excluded from our study.

Data Collection: Detailed history and medical assessment of the included patients were carried out at the time of first contact with the treating team. The patients underwent laboratory and imaging study as requested by the treating team. We collected data on age, clinical presentation and laboratory parameters on a prespecified data collection sheet.

Results

A hospital based observational research was conducted on 134 patients who attended Gauhati Medical College and Hospital between December 2023 to July 2024. The study included post-menopausal women subjects attended the medicine department of Gauhati Medical College and Hospital with a probable diagnosis of urinary tract infection. The majority of the prevalence in our study was in the age group of 44 to 52 yrs. (44%) as compared to other age groups.

Figure 1: Histogram showing age wise distribution of prevalence

The overall recurrence rate of our study was 41.35%. However, the prevalence of recurrence was highest in the age group of more than 80 yrs (77%).

Table 1: Recurrence rate age-wise

AGE (yrs.)	RECURRENCE (%)
44-49	21.8
50-59	41.6
60-69	47.62
70-79	50
>80	77.7

Table 2:

Number of UTI recurrence cases with Diabetes	Number of UTI recurrence cases without Diabetes	Number of UTI non recurrence cases with Diabetes	Number of UTI non recurrence cases without Diabetes
47	23	31	33

Table 3: Observed contingency

	UTI recurrence (Y)	UTI recurrence (N)	Total of Row
DM (Y)	47	31	78
DM (N)	23	33	56
Total column	70	64	
Total	134		

Table 4: Expected contingency

	UTI recurrence (Y)	UTI recurrence (N)
DM (Y)	40.75	37.25
DM (N)	29.25	26.75

P-value: 0.03

This means there is statistically significant association between UTI recurrence and the comorbidity DM. The recurrence of UTI in patients with Diabetes mellitus, is almost two times more likely ($p= 0.03$). The urine culture and sensitivity reports of the study population showed that the most common organism to be isolated was *E. coli* 75 (76.9%).

Figure 2: Bar diagram showing organisms that were isolated in urine culture

There was statistically significant association between the type of organism causing urinary tract infection and outcome with a p-value of 1.77269E-07 (0.000000177269). *E. coli* was found to be responsible for most of the adverse outcomes in our study, compared to other organisms like *K. pneumoniae*, *S. aureus*, *E. faecalis* and *S. saprophyticus*.

Discussion

Based on the findings of our study, the highest prevalence of UTI was seen in the age group of 44-52 years, however the rate of recurrence was highest in age group of more than 80 years.

There was statistically significant association of recurrence of UTI and DM in our study, where patients with diabetes mellitus were two times

more likely to suffer. *E. coli* was the most common organism isolated in our study from urine culture as well as the most important organism causing adverse events. Other studies conducted showed similar prevalence like the study done by Hu KK, Boyko EJ, Scholes D, et al (9) showing 9% prevalence in the age group of more than 50 yrs. But in a study conducted by Raz R. [10] showed 15% to 20% of 65–70-year-old women have bacteriuria, compared with 20% to 50% of women >80 years old.

Jung C et al [11] conducted a study, where the recurrence rate in post-menopausal women was found to be 55%. In another study conducted by Raz R et al [10], the prevalence of UTIs among women is thought to increase even further with age, with bacteriuria occurring in 10%–15% of women aged 65–70 years and 15%–20% of women aged >80 years. Our findings are similar to a study conducted by Nitzan O et al [12], where they had recurrence of UTI in diabetic patients 23%, vs 6.1%, in women without diabetes. Another study by Lim et al [13], also found higher rates of recurrence of UTI in patients with type 2 diabetes of 1.6%, vs 0.6% in non-diabetic patients.

In similar studies conducted by Flores-Mireles A. et al [14] 2015, *E. coli* was found to be the most common organism causing UTI, followed by *K. pneumoniae*. Klein R et al [15], too found similar inference in their study, where *E. coli* was responsible for 80% of the infection.

Conclusion

Based on our study it is evident that the recurrence of UTI increases with age after menopause. The presence of Diabetes Mellitus is associated with higher recurrence of the infection as well, as is with other infections. *E. coli* was found to be the most common cause of UTI in our study. It was responsible for poor outcome in our study population as well. This aligns with existing literature that shows similar outcomes as our study.

Limitation of the Study

The study results may be influenced by limitations like small sample size of our study which may not fully represent the depth of the problem. Hence larger scale studies are required to comprehensively evaluate patients with UTI presenting to OPD or emergency.

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